

1 **Cooperation between ERBB genes and the estrogen receptor.**

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6 We measured total transcription in MCF7 breast cancer cells following genetic depletion of estrogen
7 receptor alpha to identify novel genes associated with estrogen signaling in cancer cells. We identified a
8 strong genetic interaction between the ERBB growth factor gene family and ESR alpha. Cells depleted of
9 the estrogen receptor lost expression of growth factors receptors *ERBB3* and *ERBB4*. ESR1 was among
10 the ten genes whose expression was most closely regulated with ERBB3 and ERBB4 transcriptome-wide.
11 The close relationship the estrogen receptor and ERBB3 and ERBB4 possess with each other likely
12 relates to a general role for sex hormones including estrogen and testosterone and EGFR family growth
13 factor signaling in transformation.
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